

Plastic Waste and their Health Threat

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Annotation: Plastic global environmental waste and medical from problems one being their years during in nature non-degradable environment it pollutes and food to the chain come in , man to health serious threat gives birth Plastic disintegration as a result harvest has been microplastics water , food and into the air spread to the body entrance through inflammation , toxic effect , hormonal disorders and of immunity to decrease take coming can This is it scientific in the article plastic waste of management current methods of microplastics a person to the organism effect learning results and waste reduce according to international cooperation and ecological culture development issues discussion will be done.

Keywords: plastic waste, microplastic, human health, phthalates, bisphenol A, ecology, filtration, toxic effect.

Plastic of goods decomposition microplastics appearance to be take they are coming food to the chains enter , human to your health threat The last 70 years inside humanity 8.3 billion ton plastic working They released . most landfills and to the environment throw away sent . As a result water basins and soil is being polluted . Also , plastic particles man to the body also enter arrived. Vienna medicine university scientists research to the results according to , one person per week average up to 5 grams micro and nanoplastic consumption does . This and bank plastic of the card weight with equal to . Such from comparison then 5 grams per week plastic trivial to something It doesn't look like it . If year on a scale can about 250 grams plastic It comes out . This is 230 cocktail tube or 8 half liter plastic of the container weight with equal to . This substances of course human to your health negative impact shows .[1] Italian scientists of 2020 May in the month one how much healthy women's microplastics in the placenta particles Placenta only pregnancy during appearance to be member . She is a mother. and baby between substances exchange provides . Exactly placenta to the fetus arrived going substances filters .

From this except , Robert Koch institute and Germany the environment ministry researchers three year from 3 to 17 years 2.5 thousand person of the child urine and blood samples learned Researchers 15 species in 97 % of samples 11 of plastic footprints found 1.5-2 liters per day water drinker people 90 thousand per year plastic particles takes

Home part

1. Microplastics in the body entrance roads

Microplastic human to the body three main road through entrance possible :

Food and drinks by : Seafood [3] products , drink water , packaged foods and even fruits and vegetables microplastic with contaminated to be can

Air via : Microplastic particles in the air flying walking , breathing get ways through to the lungs enters

Skin via: Although skin through of plastic straight away entrance less although cosmetic tools contained microplastics this the process facilitate possible .[2]

2. Immune to the system effect

Microplastic particles to the organism from entering then , they inflammation processes cause release can Immune system a stranger to substances against while fighting inflammation reactions surface it comes while chronic of diseases development take coming can Microplastics existence of phagocytes (foreign particles winning cells) is correct work from the trail release possible .[5]

3. Endocrine to the system impact

Plastic to the composition included chemical substances (e.g. phthalates) and bisphenol A) to the body from entering then , endocrine to the system impact does :[4]

Hormonal imbalance: This substances natural hormones performance blocked to put or them imitation to do possible .

Reproductive to health damage: Microplastics male and a woman reproductive to systems damage delivery , infertility or fetus in development defects cause release can

4. Organs to the activity effect

Microplastics long term during in the body accumulation the following organs to the activity damage deliver can :

Lungs : Asthma ways through entered microplastics breath get difficulties , asthma and another chronic diseases cause release can

Liver and kidneys: Microplastics in the blood accumulation and filtration system download to put and of toxins release to the process hindrance to do can

Intestine microflora: Microplastics in the intestine microorganisms balance break it while food digestion to do with depends problems and of immunity to decrease take coming possible. [6]

Plastic waste reduce according to common recommendations

One once plastic products prohibition or of them to use reduce according to legislation strengthen.

Plastic dishes instead of again used ecological safe materials (metal , glass , bamboo and others) use .

Plastic place presser ecological safe bioplastic materials work release and publicize.

Paper , cardboard or starch based on prepared of products to use promote do.[8]

Conclusion. Summary by doing in other words , plastic of waste to health has been effect reduce issue not only ecological problem , maybe a person health provide point of view in terms of too is relevant . Plastic of waste harmful effects reduce for wide scope cooperation , scientific studies and efficient politics work exit necessary.[7] Plastic of waste a person to health effect reduce for one row measures demand will be done . These are between plastic again work and alternative of materials to use expansion , plastic waste reduction , ecological education and the public informed to do important place holds That's it with together , plastic waste manage according to strictly legislation and innovative technologies current reach necessary

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